

An Agent-Based Communication Model in Internal Communication

Eduard Buzila
Faculty of Management and Economics
Otto von Guericke University
Magdeburg
Eduard.Buzila@ovgu.de

Mirko Kämpf
Scalytics, Inc.

Internal communication (IC) is a critical driver of employee engagement and organisational success. However, traditional communication models assume dyadic, human-to-human interaction. They do not reflect the socio-technical complexities of modern workplaces shaped by conversational AI and digital assistance by smart agents. We address this gap by introducing a novel communication model for IC that integrates three special types of smart agents – World Interpreter, World Exposer, and Cognitive Enhancer – to mediate communication, to establish common ground, and to manage personal, organisational, and world knowledge as part of their communication support. Drawing from philosophy, communication theory, and recent developments in AI, our model captures the shift from dyadic to triadic human-agents-human communication and supports both synchronous and asynchronous interactions. This model contributes a socio-technical lens to management and IC research. It offers a foundation for studying augmented communication practices. Furthermore, it enables future empirical studies on the impact of multi-agent communication assistance systems on collaboration, knowledge sharing, and organisational effectiveness in the corporate environments.

Keywords: augmented communication, human-agents-interaction, internal communication, large language models, knowledge worker

1. INTRODUCTION

Effective Internal Communication (EIC), meaning sharing information with, listening and giving voice to, hence involving and appreciating each individual employee within all organisational decision-making processes that might directly or indirectly affect them as the company's internal stakeholders, is widely recognised as one of the cornerstones of organisational and business success (Men, 2015; Pološki Vokić et al., 2020; Smith & Mounter, 2008; Yates, 2006; Yue et al., 2025). The reason why EIC is so crucial is because it directly influences employee engagement, wellbeing, loyalty, organisational commitment, and consequently the employee and firm productivity (Bakker et al., 2011; Bakker & Schaufeli, 2008; Cai et al., 2018; Clampitt & Downs, 1993; Jones, 1997; Kahn, 1990, 1992; Lalić et al., 2020; Mbhele & de Beer, 2021; Romero-Rodríguez & Castillo-Abdul, 2024; Saks, 2019; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004; Sinitsyna et al., 2024; Tkalac Verčič & Men, 2023; Walden, 2021; Welch, 2011; Y. Zhang et al., 2022).

The seminal Hawthorne Studies (1924-1933) of employees at the Western Electric Company in Chicago (Roethlisberger & Dickson, 1939) were one of the earliest quantitative and qualitative inquiries that empirically showed the positive effects of EIC on employee engagement (Jensen, 2021), which can be defined as “the individual's involvement and satisfaction with as well as enthusiasm for work” (Harter et al., 2002, p. 269). Ever since Taylor (1919)'s *Principles of Scientific Management* and the Hawthorne Studies, it has become common knowledge that employees, who are happy, are, at least most of the time, also productive (Warr, 1987; Wright et al., 2007; Wright & Cropanzano, 2007), and thus play a crucial role in enabling the leadership of an enterprise to accomplish the company's business success (Dortok, 2006). Consequently, the establishment of an effective communication department (J.

Cornelissen, 2020; Zerfass & Link, 2022), which is responsible for internal and external communication, is as important as other departments, including marketing, sales, finance, human resources, and information technology (IT) for the company's business success (Ingelmo Palomares et al., 2018). Other authors such as Brockhaus and Zerfass (2022) even believe that an IC department is the most important one of all. This importance is derived from the potentiality of IC to "effectively convey the values of the organization to all employees, and involve them with the goals of the organization" (Welch, 2011, p. 339). Therefore, from a management perspective, the top management team of a company has to ensure that the executive team, commonly known as the C-Suite, successfully implements EIC strategies (Men, 2015; Smith & Mounter, 2008) to contribute to the company's business success. In this vein, Welch and Jackson (2007) conceptualise senior management communication as internal corporate communication that must include all departments and employees. Smythe (2007) also argues that a Chief Executive Officer (CEO)'s main concern must be IC management.

Yates (2006, p. 71) regards EIC even as a "secret weapon", as research conducted by Watson Wyatt Worldwide (now Willis Towers Watson) in 2003 and 2005 indicated that companies with superior IC achieved greater market premiums, higher returns for stakeholders over a five-year period, enhanced employee engagement, and reduced staff turnover compared to companies with less effective communication practices. EIC represents therefore a fundamental organisational phenomenon, directly tied to managerial processes such as coordination, sensemaking, employee engagement, and strategic alignment – all of which are central concerns within management research (Cristofaro, 2022; Eckstein et al., 2024; Gerow et al., 2014; Ruben & Gigliotti, 2016; Tourish & Robson, 2006; Wu et al., 2015). Especially employee engagement

embodies “a need for employee communication to understand and serve internal stakeholders’ core [...] communication needs, as well as surface [...] communication needs” (Welch, 2011, p. 336). This personal communication requires those in a leadership position to communicate effectively to their employees in order to reach out to each individual one in “a personal, intimate way” (Men & Tsai, 2016, p. 932) while their employees also have to possess communication skills to effectively communicate to their colleagues and supervisors to provide them with feedback in order to prevent or solve potential issues, and to increase their own satisfaction (Mazzei, 2010; Snyder & Morris, 1984; Stehle, 2023; Thelen, 2021; Tkalac Verčič & Pološki Vokić, 2017). In this vein, Johansson et al. (2014, p. 147) define a communicative leader “as someone who engages employees in dialogue, actively shares and seeks feedback, practices participative decision making, and is perceived as open and involved”. The communication abilities, skills, and competence of such leaders are salient factors in driving employee engagement (Brønn, 2014; Penley et al., 1991; Wiley et al., 2010). This also shows that employee engagement requires both sides to effectively communicate with each other. Hence, it also requires communicative employees that actively share and provide feedback to their leaders. As such, the direction of the information flow in IC should not be exclusively unilateral – neither top-down (from the management team to the operational-level staff) nor bottom-up (from the operational-level staff to the management team) –, it also should not be exclusively bilateral – horizontal (between colleagues and departments) –, but rather multidirectional and multilateral in order to intentionally include all employees as the addressees of an EIC on their individual participation level.

Traditionally, IC has been examined through the lens of organisational studies (Dickson et al., 2003; Hargie & Tourish, 1993; Manning, 1992; Quinn & Hargie, 2004;

Robson & Tourish, 2005), human resources (Luthans & Youssef, 2004), public relations (Lee & Yue, 2020; Tkalac Verčič, 2025), marketing (Ahmed & Rafiq, 2003; Jacobsen et al., 2014), to name but a few (Araújo & Miranda, 2020; Tkalac Verčič et al., 2012). IC also intersects with fields such as psychology (Krishna, 2022; Romero-Rodríguez & Castillo-Abdul, 2024), ethnography (Browning et al., 2022; Verheyden, 2017), linguistics (Hendriks & Mulken, 2012; Louhiala-Salminen & Kankaanranta, 2012), and information systems (Andersen, 2001; Wuersch et al., 2023, 2024), offering fertile ground for interdisciplinary theorising in management research.

As has been shown so far, an EIC is, in general, all about communicating information to all employees (receiver) as well as giving them a voice (Ruck et al., 2017) (sender), which Van Dyne et al. (2003, p. 1360) define as “intentionally expressing relevant ideas, information, and opinions about possible improvements”. It is this dyadic organisational communication relationship (Krain, 1973; Panko & Kinney, 1992) that can be “described in terms of the ‘richness’ of informational flow between individuals” (Barry & Crant, 2000, p. 651) – where they can be a sender and a receiver linked to each other as they practice a bidirectional conversation –, which establishes the core interaction within EIC and which is the main focus of this paper.

To understand and analyse the dynamics of communication acts within an EIC, a communication model is required that functions as a theoretical framework for qualitative and quantitative research. In this paper, we propose a new model of communication that is based on interdisciplinary insights from linguistics, communication studies, information systems, and management research. We believe that such a new communication model is needed because, to our knowledge, there are no other communication models that have incorporated all the new communication technologies and all the new software that are based on Artificial Intelligence (AI). In

particular, there are, again to our knowledge, no communication models that have been designed specifically for understanding and analysing EIC that is based and mediated by AI technologies, and by AI-driven and AI-based artefacts and systems. As such, the aim of our paper is to present a new communication model that incorporates the aforementioned technologies and that can be used as a framework to conduct qualitative and quantitative research in the area of EIC.

Our paper is organised as follows. In the first part of the paper, in Section 2 and 3, we draw on past research and theory in philosophy, linguistics, communication studies, and information systems to examine the dyadic organisational human-human relationship of a sender and a receiver within the framework of EIC. For this reason, we will make recourse to communication models, which are characterised by a human-centric perspective, showcasing how a message is being transported between two human interlocutors. The advent of new communication technologies, however, has changed the way in which employees communicate to each other, and to their managers. Consequently, it has also changed the dyadic human-human relationship by including this technology, forming a triadic human-agents-human communication relationship.

In the second part of the paper, in Section 4 and 5, we propose a new communication model for an EIC that extends and updates the previously discussed models. The current new forms of communication have been made possible by the advent of new powerful AI tools such as ChatGPT, Co-Pilot, and other – often invisibly integrated assistant systems – that have profoundly influenced IC. The aim of our communication model is thus to provide an explanation for how the dyadic organisational human-human relationship has been transformed to a triadic organisational human-agents-human relationship. This way, our communication model lays the foundation for

composing and studying complex communication scenarios within loosely coupled groups and across organisational structures. Furthermore, adding more agents to the human-human relationship, our model cannot only be applied to triadic but also to 1: N human-agents-relationships. Following this new socio-technical modelling path, we aim to contribute to interdisciplinary research and to provide an innovative modelling technique for communication processes, especially EIC. Additionally, our communication model should also function as a theoretical framework that can be used to carry out quantitative and qualitative research in the field of EIC. Finally, our communication model has also practical implications since it can help C-level managers to take many factors into account that are crucial when contemplating about the implementation of assistant systems into the company.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND THE EVOLUTION OF COMMUNICATION MODELS

In this section we look at EIC through the lens of the philosophy of language to develop the philosophical and anthropological foundation for the discussion of the traditional human-centric communication models. The reason why they are human-centric is because of the assumption that communication takes place exclusively between humans, who therefore form the axiomatic foundation of all communication models. Every human interlocutor in the model is axiomatically assumed to be a *homo loquens*, meaning a speaking human (Baron, 2015; Fry, 1977; Matthews, 2003; Pulgram, 1970), who possesses and uses language as a medium to transport a message. Moreover, the models also assume that both *homini*, both interlocutors, are sender and receiver at the same time (Makkai, 1995). The philosophical foundation of the *homo loquens* lies in the 18th century, where the most esteemed European philosophers were discussing the origin of language and argued that the ability to communicate through language fundamentally shapes human thought, identity, culture, and social interaction.

In 1769, the Royal Prussian Academy of Sciences announced a prize question that read: “Abandoned to their natural capacities, would human beings be in a condition to invent language? And by what means could they achieve this invention on their own?” (Lifschitz, 2012, p. 178) The Prussian philosopher Johann Gottfried Herder took part in this “essay competition on the hottest language theme of the century” and submitted in 1771 his *Treatise on the Origin of Language* (Trabant, 2009, p. 122), with which he won the first prize, and “which is perhaps Herder’s most beautiful and certainly most influential work” (Trabant, 2009, p. 123). Published in 1772, this essay is regarded by some scholars as “an epoch-making contribution to the history of linguistics, disposing

once and for all of the tradition hypothesis that language is the direct gift of God to man, and the alternative materialist explanations, going back to classical antiquity, that human language arose from the specialization of animal cries, and that men had somehow devised language by agreement” (Salmon, 1989, p. 25).

Herder famously expresses this in the very first sentence of his essay by stating: “Already as an animal, the human being has language” (Herder, 2002b, p. 65). By this, he argues that there has never been a point in time in which animals or humans were languageless. They have always possessed language, namely an “animal language”, which they use for the expression of passions and sensations, and for communication (Trabant, 2009, p. 123), i.e. for an “instinctual communication” (Fry, 1977, p. 2), since their mental and physical properties for language production are innate. What distinguishes humans from animals is, according to Herder, the humans’ innate disposition of thought generation combined with their need to gain knowledge of the world (“Besonnenheit”) (Trabant, 2009, p. 124). Whenever humans think about themselves or the world – either internally (internal dialogue) or externally (external dialogue) –, they require language because without it, no thought can emerge. Hence, Herder states: “We think in language” (Herder, 2002a, p. 49), which is primarily thought, and “thought is the world”, and “the soul listens to the world” (Trabant, 2009, pp. 124, 128). As such, “Herder’s *Besonnenheit* invents language through contact with the world; experience of the world triggers the ‘sense’ or the ‘organ’ of language into operation” (Trabant, 2009, p. 128). Hearing and speaking are for him the most crucial senses that shape language. Hence, “knowing is no longer seeing, it is hearing”, it is “listening to the sounds of the world”, which are reproduced by the mouth (Trabant, 2009, pp. 128, 129). And since humans do not live in isolation, but form communities with others, since they form societies, language is one ingredient of “the cement”

(Elster, 1989) that keeps societies together through constant dialogues within themselves as well as with others. The sound of each language is thus a reflection of each of these societies since they sound differently, which is why Herder believes in linguistically diverse nations:

I cannot think the first human thought, cannot set up the first aware judgement in a sequence, without engaging in dialogue, or striving to engage in dialogue, in my soul. Hence the first human thought by its very nature prepares one to be able to engage in dialogue with others! The first *characteristic mark* that I grasp is a *characteristic word* for me and a *communication word* for others! (Herder, 2002b, p. 97)

Following Herder's line of reasoning, an EIC can be viewed through the lens of the *homo loquens* as it highlights that communication within organisations is not merely instrumental but fundamental to employees' identities, perceptions, and interactions. The organisational entity, the company, brings its employees together, but what keeps them all together, is communication. Hence, organisations constitute communication communities or hubs of communicating humans, whose sense-making, collaboration, and productivity depend upon the quality and nature of their communicative practices. Communication in general and IC in particular functions within an organisation as the "cement" (Elster, 1989) or, as Wiesenfeld et al. (1999, p. 777) put it, as the "glue" that keeps all employees together by forming an organisational identity (Huff et al., 1989; Sproull & Kiesler, 1986; Yue et al., 2021). Communication thus shapes organisational identity as employees continuously construct shared meanings, shared interpretive context among organisation members, experiences, and memories as well as organisational culture, and collective narratives through language (Zack, 1993). Managers and leaders, who recognise employees as *homo loquens*, understand that

communication is more than information transfer – it is inherently tied to human dignity, meaning-making, and relational dynamics within an organisation.

Over one hundred years later, the philosophy of language developed by Herder and others in the 18th and 19th century was extended and modelled by Saussure's structural approach to language and communication, which was posthumously published as the *Cours de linguistique générale* in 1916. Saussure (1989, p. 14), who is acknowledged as the father of modern linguistics (Y. Zhang & Zhang, 2021), argued that linguists have to study "language as a structured system", and this unified system is made out of an abstract, arbitrary system of signs, governed by rules (*la langue*) – the speaker's competence to use the rules of the sign system (grammar) –, and of acts of speech (*la parole*) – the speaker's performance, e.g., speech or writing. Saussure viewed language as the combination of *langue* and *parole*, which function as a vehicle that transports a message from one speaker to another. As illustrated in Figure 1, the act of communication takes place within the so-called "speech circuit" (Saussure, 1989, pp. 11–12), which links the two interlocutors. The message that speaker A wants to communicate is stored in his brain. He then uses his vocal organs to generate a sign (word), which is arbitrary (conventional), to transport his message to speaker B, who receives the sign auditorily through his ear, and associates the sound of the sign with an image stored in his brain. In response to A, B also uses a sign vocally to verbally compose a message that is transported to A by sound waves, received by the ear, and processes mentally. Now the speech circuit is closed.

Figure 1 Saussure's Speech Circuit (Saussure, 1989, p. 9)

Saussure's revolutionary contribution is his development of a model of communication that focuses on "the language systems stored in the brains of individual language users" (Daylight, 2017, p. 175). Similar to Herder, Saussure believed that humans did not invent language as a tool for communication but that language exists *a priori*, and because it already exists, because it is "among the speakers, like water among fishes in the sea", humans just use it for communication (Cimatti, 2022, pp. 38–39).

AN OVERVIEW OF COMMUNICATION MODELS

Table 1 outlines a range of influential communication models that are, at least implicitly, based on the concept of *homo loquens* and Saussure's sender-receiver model as their point of departure. Both sender and receiver are conceptualised as a *homo loquens*, who sends a message from one to the other. Each communication model is deeply rooted in its respective historical and disciplinary context, and is an adjustment of Saussure's initial communication model in order to explain new emerging phenomena that are linked to *langue* and *parole*, and often inspired by technological process and changes in society.

Model	Characteristics of the Model	Mode of Communication	Feedback	Discipline/Field
Saussure's Model (1916)	Structural linguistics; meaning through signs; sender-receiver interaction as symbolic exchange	Linear	No explicit	Linguistics, Semiotics
Lasswell's Model (1948)	Mass media communication; communication effects and persuasion in society	Linear	No explicit	Media Studies, Political Science
Shannon-Weaver Model (1949)	Technical communication; reducing noise, clarity in signal transmission	Linear	No explicit	Information Theory, Engineering
Schramm's Interactive Model (1954)	Interaction, feedback loops, shared understanding, and overlapping fields of experience between communicators	Interactive	Explicit	Communication Studies
Jakobson's Model (1960)	Multifunctional nature of language; context-sensitive communication highlighting linguistic functions (expressive, conative, referential, phatic, poetic, metalingual)	Interactive	Implicit	Linguistics, Literary Studies
Berlo's SMCR Model (1960)	Psychological and cultural influences on the sender-receiver process; the roles of knowledge, attitudes, social structures, and communication skills.	Linear	Implicit	Psychology, Communication Studies

The trajectory of communication theory closely mirrors broader developments in technology and society. In 1948, Lasswell (1948), who is considered the founding father of political psychology (Post, 2001), presented a model of communication based on the following elements: Who / Says What / In Which Channel / To Whom / With What Effect? With his model he addressed the rise of mass media and its social

function. His approach, although seemingly straightforward, signalled the beginning of a new era in which communication was increasingly viewed through the lens of technological mediation and social relevance, and consequently as a new and emerging discipline (Lasswell, 1958).

Figure 2 Lasswell's Model of Communication (Sapienza et al., 2015)

Between 1949 and 1960, additional foundational communication models emerged, most notably from Shannon, Schramm, and Jakobson. Shannon (1948), known as the father of information theory (Floridi, 2010), developed a mathematical theory of communication that is grounded in telecommunication engineering, framing communication in terms of signal transmission, channel reliability, and the mathematics of information. In their book, Shannon and Weaver (1949) generalised the model further to what has become known as the Shannon-Weaver Model, which is the first model that describes the entire process in which a signal transfers from one side to the other (H. L. Li, 2007). As can be seen in Figure 3, the model does not explicitly contain humans since it focuses solely on the technical aspect of Knowledge Transfer (Sveiby, 1996). Consequently, it cannot be applied to interpersonal communication (Bowman & Targowski, 1987), and hence not to IC (Lewis, 2006). Notwithstanding, there is a human sender and receiver in this model but they are modelled exogenously.

Figure 3 The Shannon-Weaver Model (Shannon & Weaver, 1949)

Schramm (1954), considered to be the founder of the field of communication studies (Schramm, 1997), expanded on previous models, especially on Lasswell (1948)'s, and developed the encoder-message-decoder model, in which he introduced the role of feedback that he describes as a “reversal of the flow, an opportunity for communicators to react quickly to signs resulting from the signs they have put out” (1973, p. 51). With the introduction of feedback into his communication model, Schramm showcases the interactive nature of communication since a dyadic communication situation always requires feedback from the interlocutors otherwise without it there is no dialogue. Hence, Schramm models communication as a circular process, which is very similar to Saussure’s speech circuit.

Figure 4 Schramm's Model of Communication (Steinberg, 1997)

Jakobson (1960)'s model of communication, as a response to Shannon and Weaver (1949), added further depth by highlighting the multifunctionality of language, and the role of contextual sensitivity in shaping communicative intent. According to Daylight (2017, pp. 183–184), Jakobson's model "creates the field of 'Communications' as we know it today, as the investigation of all aspects of the communication of a message, from the intentions of the sender, to the media through which it is transmitted, to the real world it refers to, and the socio-political environment in which it is received".

Figure 5 Jakobson's Model of Communication Based on his Six Constituent Factors of Communication (Lemon, 2018)

By 1960, Berlo (1960), based on Schramm (1954), and in response to Shannon and Weaver (1949)'s model, brought a psychological lens to the field, integrating cognitive and emotional processes into his model of communication that is also known as the SMCR model, which stands for "Sender, Message, Channel, and Receiver". These components of the communication process provide a structure that explains how communication takes place. While the mathematical model of communication is concerned with how adequate a channel is, Berlo's communication model focuses on factors that influence effective communication, emphasising the Source and the Receiver in particular.

Figure 6 Berlo's SMCR Model (1960)

Taken together, these six communication models reflect a distinctly interdisciplinary evolution – from philosophy, linguistics to engineering and psychology – each offering a unique perspective shaped by its disciplinary concerns.

While all of these models share communication as their central concern, the disciplinary differences reveal varied epistemological priorities. More than descriptive tools, these models serve as analytical frameworks for exploring the complexity of communication systems in their respective contexts. Yet, as technologies evolve – particularly in the direction of agent-based systems – it becomes clear that these classical models require adaptation. Contemporary communication increasingly involves artificially intelligent communication technologies and machine agents capable of interacting with, mediating, and even generating communicative acts (Bermúdez et al., 2007; Endacott & Leonardi, 2022; Soon et al., 2019). In light of this, we propose a conceptual extension that integrates these new dynamics into existing frameworks.

GENERALISATION OF EXISTING COMMUNICATION MODELS

Figure 7 presents a schematic overview of three typical foundational communication models, each illustrating distinct characteristics and evolutions in the theory of human communication which has been collected in Table 1.

In the first model in Figure 7 (a), communication is represented as a unidirectional transmission process between a sender and a receiver (Shannon & Weaver, 1949). A message is transmitted from one interlocutor to another one without consideration for contextual or interpretive elements. This model, which closely aligns with Shannon and Weaver (1949)'s information theory framework, focuses exclusively on the forward transmission of data. It omits critical dimensions such as the meaning, intent, effect, and content quality of the message. These omissions reflect the model's purely technical orientation toward communication as signal transfer.

The second model, depicted in Figure 7 (b), introduces a feedback loop (Schramm, 1954). Here, communication is conceptualised as a sequence of request and response activities between two interacting interlocutors. The roles of the sender and receiver are no longer fixed; each interlocutor may initiate or respond to communication, reflecting a dynamic, oscillating exchange of messages. This model captures the interactive nature of communication but remains limited in its treatment of comprehensibility or mutual understanding between interlocutors. It emphasises the presence of interaction and feedback, rather than the semantic or interpretive alignment between participants.

The third model builds further by incorporating the notion of common ground, which Clark (1996, p. 92) defines as "a *sine qua non* for everything we do with others". Common ground is thus a foundational set of shared understandings and experiences

that makes meaningful communication possible (Tolzin & Janson, 2025). In this view, successful interaction does not merely rely on signal exchange or behavioural responsiveness, but on overlapping mental models, shared language, mutual expectations, and cultural alignment. Common ground may be shaped by communication, prior experience, institutional memory, emotional affinity, or shared goals (Ferraro & Beunza, 2018; Gervits et al., 2016; Hayashi & Miwa, 2009; Zheng & Breheny, 2021). It is dynamic and context-sensitive, forming the substrate upon which mutual understanding is constructed. This model thus shifts focus from the mechanics of message delivery to the anthropological, social, psychological, cognitive and relational conditions that enable communication to succeed.

Figure 7 Generalisation of Existing Communication Models

THE NEED FOR AN EXTENDED MODEL

However, even this enriched model in Figure 7 has its limitations when applied to emerging forms of digital communication, particularly those involving *intelligent agents*. As human-machine interactions become more prevalent in organisational, technical, and everyday settings, it becomes necessary to expand the framework further (Hoc, 2000; Nardo et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2024; Zanatto et al., 2024). Our proposed extension addresses this need by integrating a *technological communication layer* that is capable of both, mediating and actively shaping the communication process.

This additional layer accounts for the increasing role of devices such as telephones, video conferencing systems, and asynchronous communication platforms. These tools do more than just to transmit information; they structure or disrupt the temporal and cognitive flow of information (Kornberger, 2017; Moody & Wu, 2013). While essential, such devices lack interpretive agency – they do not contribute to meaning, only to delivery and information availability.

By contrast, *multi-agent systems* – and particularly smart agents (Leitao et al., 2016) – introduce a qualitatively new capacity: the ability to actively establish or augment common ground between interlocutors (Davis, 2025). Rather than assuming a shared context, these agents are able to retrieve, interpret, and align contextual information from both participants. This ability enables them to mediate between otherwise disconnected cognitive environments and foster shared understanding where none previously existed. In effect, the agent does not merely pass messages; it participates in meaning-making.

Figure 8, and specifically subfigure (b), visualises this conceptual shift. It illustrates how the smart agent intervenes between two communication contexts, constructing

the common ground required for interaction. In contrast, subfigure (a) depicts a situation in which common ground is assumed, not established, which is predominantly related to the existing communication models. The distinction is crucial: it marks the transition from models that describe communication as the transfer of information to models that treat communication as a dynamic, collaborative construction of understanding. In this light, the agent becomes not just a conduit but a co-constructor of communicative reality.

Figure 8 The so-called Common Ground can be a Prerequisite; (a) in order to make Technical Communication Devices useful in Communication, (b) it can be induced by the Augmented Communication Environment

Our contribution addresses the “growing concern that these concepts are routinely under-represented, misrepresented and their importance seriously underplayed in the study of management generally, and particularly in the study of the information systems and digital technologies that underpin so much of business operations, personal and social life, organisation, communication and management today” (Mingers & Willcocks, 2023, p. xiii)

3. COMMUNICATION THEORY

SYNCHRONOUS VS. ASYNCHRONOUS COMMUNICATION

A variety of technical devices and digital systems have influenced and changed human communication over time. It all started with the invention of writing (Smith & Mounter, 2008; Steinberg, 1997). Using symbols and the written word as an enabler of asynchronous communication can be seen as an important milestone in human civilization. Later on, by using more and more technology for automation of the publishing process and finally switching to digital text processing and text-based message exchange we can see a big shift in the way how communication is used by human on a personal level, and also by groups within society. Digital information systems go beyond the written word. They offer voice transfer and voice conservation. Thus, the human aspect of face-to-face communication is resembled and the advantage of asynchronous communication can still be applied. So far, the common ground has been a fundamental element of successful communication. But now, using another type of technology, we can see again a drastic change in communication patterns. Instead of a synchronous human-to-human communication we can envision a meeting, in-person, but based on a proposed agenda which has been extracted by both person's agents. This way, the agents prepare or establish the common ground.

Asynchronous communication is very important from a resource utilisation perspective. The decoupling of processes and the reduction of the number of synchronisation points reduce potential waiting times. At the same time, the availability of a service or a resource increases, as soon as asynchronous consumption – in this case in the form of asynchronous communication – becomes the norm.

Aspect	Synchronous Communication	Asynchronous Communication
Essential Properties	Real-time; both participants are present and engaged at the same time	Time-shifted; participants interact on their own schedules.
Human Analogy	A live conversation — face-to-face, phone, video call.	Written communication — email, voicemail, letters, text messages
Presence	Sender and receiver are both “live” — attention is shared.	Sender and receiver are decoupled in time — response can be delayed.
Feedback	Immediate — verbal or non-verbal cues guide the conversation	Delayed — no feedback loop until the recipient replies.
Coordination	Requires coordination to meet/talk at the same time.	No coordination needed — interaction happens asynchronously.
Cognitive Load	High in the moment, but supports negotiation, repair, and nuance.	Lower immediate load, but requires memory/context recall on reply.
Information Richness	High — body language, tone, and real-time reactions	Lower — relies on clarity of message, written tone, or metadata.

Current IC strategies apply a mixture of all possible communication systems, tools, devices, and concepts, which all share the above-mentioned properties (Hudcová, 2014; Martínez Sánchez & Villoro Armengol, 2021; Tkalac Verčič et al., 2025). Many of them allow asynchronous communication but employees try to use them in a synchronous way (Fuchs & Reichel, 2023; Rishani et al., 2025; Toebben et al., 2025). In the other case, the asynchronous nature is misinterpreted and misunderstood. As a consequence, employees have misaligned communication and information loss. Many of them lack a clear understanding of the properties of the specific communication mode. The reasons for this can be personal experience and expectations or badly defined company rules including bad habits. In cases, where communication modes are not well understood, smart agent systems might have the potential to improve the communication processes.

The duality of asynchronous and synchronous communication is an approach to capture communication as it happens, and to handle the information flow in a minimal intrusive approach for both parties (Nagel et al., 2023). As a consequence, existing resources, and capabilities can be utilised at a much higher level.

These assumptions seem to be intuitively clear, but must be analysed further. Hence, we define our communication model in order to providing a framework for systematic research on the effects of smart communication agents. Table 2 summarises properties of synchronous and asynchronous communication modes.

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EIC

AI is becoming a significant part of both our personal and professional lives, particularly through the use of conversational agents (CAs). However, when these systems fail, it disrupts communication between humans and the agents, reducing their effectiveness (Tolzin & Janson, 2025). AI is designed to replicate certain aspects of human intelligence, which allows it to engage in conversations that resemble human dialogue (Elshan et al., 2022). These agents work by interacting with users to help them accomplish tasks. They learn and adapt over time, and are recognised as a distinct type of information system due to their ability to both process information intelligently and engage in dialogue (Elshan et al., 2022).

Unlike humans, though, CAs operate based on predefined rules or large language models (LLMs), and this foundational difference often leads to communication breakdowns. These misunderstandings make the interaction feel unnatural and can

result in users becoming frustrated or disillusioned with the technology (Benner et al., 2021). In some cases, the agent might respond incorrectly, fail to respond at all, or generate confusing output. Such issues can lead to negative user experiences and may cause people to stop using the technology altogether, hindering its broader adoption (Luger & Sellen, 2016; Weiler et al., 2022). This makes it clear that improving how humans and CAs communicate should be a priority for both researchers and developers. After all, successful communication depends on a dynamic, mutual process of understanding (Tolzin & Janson, 2025).

Despite the ambiguity of language, human communication generally works well. This is largely because people work together to establish shared understanding, or what's known as "common ground" (Clark & Brennan, 1991). This ongoing process – called conversational grounding – involves building mutual awareness, shared beliefs, and aligned expectations throughout the dialogue (Koulouri et al., 2016). According to Tolzin and Janson (2025), common ground is formed through the shared and individual knowledge, assumptions, and expectations that conversation partners bring into and build upon during their interaction.

IC also plays a vital role in engaging employees (Mbhele & de Beer, 2021). Its purpose is to influence employee behaviour and decision-making through clear, intentional messaging. But communication is not just about sending messages – it is just as important that the messages are understood and acted upon. As workplaces evolve and new trends and technologies emerge, existing communication theories and practices need to be updated. Research in IC has historically lagged behind real-world

practice, though recent years have seen notable progress in bridging that gap (Men, 2021).

Tools such as written notes, phones, video calls, or even digital assistants can all support and enrich human interaction. This broader idea of support is sometimes referred to as "augmented communication." Originally, the term described how people with speech impairments used technology to aid communication (Pinner, 2019). However, it has since expanded to include enhancements that benefit all speakers, even those without disabilities, in everyday conversation (Pinner, 2019).

Modern AI-based agents now represent a new form of augmented communication. They have a direct influence on how communication happens within organisations and, by extension, on management activities. Yet, current communication models – whether in linguistics or IC – do not fully account for the role of AI and agent-based systems. This gap presents an opportunity for further research.

To address this, we introduce a new communication model that incorporates multiple agents. This model reflects the complexity of today's real-world communication scenarios and aims to serve as a foundation for future studies at the intersection of IC and management research.

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION AND MANAGEMENT

IC is distinct from related disciplines such as organisational, business, or management communication (Men, 2021, p. 8). One area where this distinction becomes particularly

evident is in the use of internal social media (ISM). For instance, in an organisation that fostered a competitive atmosphere, ISM failed to support a diversity of voices. In contrast, in two other, more open organisational cultures, ISM evolved into a platform where employees – regardless of rank or position – felt encouraged to contribute. This suggests that employees are not only cautious of potential repercussions from management, but also of how their peers might respond (Madsen, 2021).

Meaningful engagement through ISM seems to emerge only when employees feel they are genuinely permitted to question or critique company policies and decisions without fearing negative reactions from colleagues or superiors (Madsen, 2021). Creating such an open environment takes time. Employees must learn how to express their views constructively and confidently, while managers must become comfortable with the idea that critical feedback is not a sign of defiance or disloyalty (Madsen, 2021).

ISM must also compete with other technologies increasingly embedded in IC, including tools powered by AI and machine learning. These technologies are now commonly used to streamline workflows and facilitate the sharing of knowledge (Madsen, 2021). When combined with ISM, AI can help identify the relevance and appeal of different types of content. This data can then be used to improve digital tools such as chatbots, which may, for example, respond to staff queries or customise the layout of an intranet homepage to match an individual employee's needs (Madsen, 2021).

Organisations are increasingly adopting ISM as a central element of their IC strategies (O'Neil et al., 2021). They now have the ability to schedule tailored messages and allow employees to select the timing and type of content they wish to receive – often via chatbots. This increases both the relevance of internal messages and the likelihood they will be read. Employees can also ask chatbots for additional details or clarification. In some cases, these chatbots are integrated into enterprise messaging platforms, making it easier to share large volumes of data and foster collaboration – particularly in sectors like software development, where such practices are already well established (O'Neil et al., 2021).

As chatbots become more prominent in the workplace, IC professionals will take on a central role in their design and management. Employees' experiences with these tools will likely influence how they perceive the organisation as a whole. Trust and organisational reputation may, therefore, be shaped – at least in part – by how successfully these technologies are implemented and used. As such, it becomes important to measure how staff perceptions of chatbots relate to broader impressions of trust and credibility within the company (O'Neil et al., 2021).

There is also growing interest in understanding how emerging technologies like AI affect employee engagement and response to IC. These tools do not simply assist with message delivery – they also shape how communication unfolds within an organisation and influence broader aspects of organisational culture and structure (O'Neil et al., 2021).

It is within this context that we propose a human-agents-human communication model. Our motivation is both practical and theoretical. Building on the work of O'Neil et al. (2021) and others, and with a particular focus on management research, we aim to introduce a comprehensive framework that accounts for the role of modern technologies in today's IC processes. This model is designed to reflect the realities of augmented communication, supported by rapidly evolving digital tools – including, potentially, future multi-agent systems. Our intention is to contribute a flexible and universally applicable socio-technical model that remains relevant, regardless of the specific technologies used in its implementation.

4. MULTI-AGENT-COMMUNICATION MODEL FOR IC AND MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

This new communication model introduces the concept of *Smart Agents* as integral components in the mediation and enhancement of human communication. From the perspective of an individual participant – referred here as the communication partner – three distinct categories of *Smart Agents* can be identified, each fulfilling a specific functional role in the bidirectional flow of information at a pairwise communication. Before defining the communication flow from communication partner 1 to communication partner 2, we focus on one communication partner that is surrounded by three characteristic information flows as shown in Figure 9.

How information flows through a communication partner via agent support.

How agents connect a communication partner to the world (A), to others (B), and to the inner dialogue (C).

Figure 9 Structural Foundation of our Multi-Agent Communication Model: The Communication Partner (in blue) is the Center of our Model. It is Connected via three Typical Information Flows – to the World (A), to Others (B), and to the Inner Dialogue

First, the *World Interpreter* (Agent A) facilitates the intake of information from the external world to the communication partner. This agent supports perception, comprehension, and contextual interpretation of incoming data, making the external environment more accessible.

Second, the *World Exposer* (Agent B) assists in the outward flow of information from the communication partner to others. It translates internal states, intentions, or expressions into forms that are interpretable by external systems or individuals, thereby making the communication partner more accessible to the outside world.

Third, the *Cognitive Enhancer* (Agent C) operates within the cognitive domain of the communication partner. It leverages the communication partner's internal context – such as prior knowledge, goals, or situational awareness – to augment reasoning, to support decision-making and communicative effectiveness. This agent mediates and enriches both inbound and outbound communication, increasing the communication partner's overall communicative capability.

When two communication partners interact, their respective agent systems establish interlinked communication channels. For instance, the *World Interpreter* (A) of one communication partner may retrieve information via the *World Exposer* (B) of the other partner. This way, Agent A accesses the representational output of Agent B, enabling the bidirectional exchange of information. This configuration results in two parallel request-response channels, one in each direction, mediated through complementary agent components, which simultaneously assist each communication partner.

Together, these *Smart Agents* form a distributed cognitive and communicative architecture that extends the capabilities of human communicators. This framework

does not only model individual interaction with information but also lays the foundation for understanding complex agent-mediated human-to-human communication systems.

KNOWLEDGE LOCATION

This section explores the locus and typology of knowledge within communicative contexts. Herder (2002b, p. 49) identified the ear as the primary organ through which knowledge is acquired, emphasising the role of auditory perception. On an individual's micro-level, Herder assumes the knowledge to be located at the ear. We interpret this on the metaphorical level and ask: Where is the organisational knowledge located? According to Sproull and Kiesler (1986, p. 1492), in the modern management context, there is a huge imbalance in distribution of knowledge and information within organisations, which leads to the famously noted saying: "The boss is always the last one to know". This illustrates how communication gaps can shield leaders from unnecessary details but also prevent access to essential knowledge, potentially leading to poor outcomes. In addition to this, the current information overload that can be observed in companies often hides relevant information so that decision processes cannot really benefit from existing knowledge (Saxena & Lamest, 2018; Sweet et al., 2025). However, when considering today's individual communication practice, which goes far beyond the spoken word by relying on technical devices and intense media support, it is more accurate to recognise the role of the full spectrum of sensory input in the perception and construction of knowledge on the human level. Even recent developments in LLM architecture go towards this direction.

The developments of LLMs such as the Qwen2.5 model family represent a new architecture that accepts multimodal input, including text, images, video, and audio signals, instead of relying solely on text representations (Qwen et al., 2025). This further improves the capability of LLMs that were initially dependent on the presence of text-based information. Through these advancements, these models are now capable of capturing the information flow in a more efficient and cost-effective way. As a result, digital learning procedures and the preservation of practical knowledge are becoming more accessible and manageable for organizations.

Hence, from the perspective of the interlinked communication of multiple interlocutors, we propose a distinction between three interrelated categories of knowledge: *Personal Knowledge*, *Organisational Knowledge*, and *World Knowledge*.

Personal Knowledge emerges through multisensory experiences, not limited to spoken language. It encompasses information absorbed through visual, auditory, tactile, and other sensory modalities. *Personal Knowledge* is physically bound to the human body, who carries it through the world. External usage of this knowledge requires communication or direct action by the individual, who possesses this knowledge.

Organisational Knowledge, by contrast, refers to a collectively shared knowledge base, often embodied in digital artefacts such as documents or media assets. This type of knowledge serves as a persistent, accessible reference point and forms part of the communicative common ground between communication partners.

World Knowledge is persisted in the digital corpus of documents created by humans, collected in libraries, and also shared digitally via the world wide web, to name just a few. In our model, we focus on the digital representation of the *World Knowledge*

because for today's digital agents, information must be present in a digital form, before learning and reasoning over that content can be achieved. Web search has been established as a very important source for information retrieval during the last three decades.

With the advent of LLMs we can see a new trend of knowledge representation and conservation. The training of such LLMs seems to conserve knowledge within the model. For our work, we do not need to go deeper into the mechanics of these processes – for our communication model it is not relevant how they work in detail – but we simply assume that the capability of processing human language is provided by the LLM. Furthermore, we create our communication model on top of the following two capabilities of modern agentic software application build around LLMs: First, the agent can access the digital *World Knowledge*, *Organisational Knowledge*, and *Personal Knowledge* via fast information retrieval processes (Ghali et al., 2025; D. Li & Xu, 2024; Ma et al., 2024; Mendoza et al., 2024; Qiao, 2024; Y. Zhang et al., 2025). Second, the agent is able to process, summarise, transform, and reason over the provided information chunks in a context sensitive and meaningful way (Delaunay et al., 2023). This is what we mean when we require the agent to be able to process human language.

Within our framework, the agent architecture plays a crucial role in mediating knowledge flow as part of the communication process. The *Type B agent* facilitates the externalisation of *Personal Knowledge*, allowing each participant to share their *Internal Knowledge States* with others. This exchange contributes to the dynamic development of a *Shared Common Ground*. To prevent cognitive overload during communication, the *Type C agent* provides contextual augmentation and cognitive

support, helping individuals process and integrate complex or large volumes of information. The *Type A agent* enables access to the *World Knowledge* – a domain of information that lies beyond the individual and organisational spheres. This includes publicly available knowledge accessible through technical interfaces, such as digital knowledge bases or web resources.

Together, these three agents support a layered and distributed knowledge framework, enhancing both individual cognition and *Shared Understanding* in mediated communication, which is established by one communication partner, and turned into a back-and-forth communication loop, where communication partners use their own knowledge and the accessible world knowledge independently as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Personal Knowledge (1), Organisational Knowledge (2), and World Knowledge (3) are Part of the Common Ground of Two Communication Partners (in blue). Our Multi-Agent Communication Model allows Multi-Lateral Conversation and thus it is suitable to serve EIC and Management Research as a Foundational Building Block for the Implementation and Analysis of Complex Communication Scenarios in the Corporate World

DUALITY OF SYNCHRONOUS AND ASYNCHRONOUS COMMUNICATION

Starting with communication partner one on the left, who has an outreaching *Communication Agent (A)*, assisted by the *Cognitive Enhancer (C)* – which is linked to its *Personal Knowledge*, to the *Company Knowledge* and to the *World Knowledge* –, a conversation can be established to the exposing agent of communication partner two. This agent (B) can automatically respond in a synchronous mode, if the request can already be answered based on existing and available knowledge. Alternatively, the asynchronous communication and a chain of background tasks can be established, in case an answer or a response cannot be provided instantly. Modelled this way, both can be decoupled and the synchronous request is transformed into an asynchronous collaboration task. This way, both communication partners are less dependent on each other but are more available to each other at the same time.

INHERENT KNOWLEDGE OR LOOKUP CAPABILITIES

The knowledge of an agent is represented by its LLM, which has been trained on relevant training data according to its domain and tasks. Training data is typically a large corpus of text data so that the model can learn the semantic structure of the used language and the content structure. New foundational models extend the capabilities of LLMs towards multi-modal operations (Qwen et al., 2025). This means they incorporate audiovisual information, like humans, who nowadays rely on multi-media communication devices.

Besides the *Inherent Knowledge*, which has been acquired during training, we can provide *Explicit Knowledge* to the agent for processing. Adding more relevant facts to

an agent's memory, influences its capabilities (Xu et al., 2025; Z. Zhang et al., 2024) as well as model training. In practical applications we must balance the way in which an agent learns new information and skills. Technically speaking, it is critical to understand when model training and when provisioning of context data is more beneficial. In this paper, we do not focus on the process of gaining the knowledge but we rather assume that the agents have access to the knowledge of the three types, which are relevant for our model (see Figure 10).

For our communication model this has two implications: First, we can assume that LLMs, which are used by different agents, differ from each other, and also evolve in different directions over time. Second, the availability of the right context data is essential for providing particular relevant knowledge to the augmented communication scenario. This is crucial for EIC and becomes increasingly more relevant in modern management. We can see that the *World Knowledge*, the *Company Knowledge*, and the *Personal Experience* can all be conserved via LLM training procedures or via data management techniques. This leads to special technical requirements regarding an organisation's IT-infrastructure and staff. For instance, digital and AI literacy become increasingly relevant aspects in modern organisations. Managing and selecting the right models and the right knowledge corpus will be a managerial task, deeply linked to the organisation's communication practice.

COMMON GROUND VS. SHARED THOUGHTS

The concept of “common ground” was initially developed in the literature on communication in organisations (Ferraro & Beunza, 2018, p. 1202). Traditional communication models treat common ground as a requirement for shared understanding (Tolzin & Janson, 2025). It is typically defined by the context of the communication process, represented by culture, experience, and technical environment in which the conversation takes place (Clark, 1996; J. P. Cornelissen & Werner, 2014). Furthermore, goals and intentions contribute to the communication ground. All these more or less given aspects are important for a better understanding of the communication processes.

With our model we aim to propose a new concept: *Shared Thoughts*, which are different from the meaning of common ground in the literature on communication in organisation but complement each other. Our own information context, which is all available data at our hand – no matter how we access and how we interpret that data – can be seen as *Shared Thoughts*, if available to both communication partners’ agents. Physically and without agents, it is not feasible to access the space of *Shared Thoughts* together with other humans since humans cannot really have shared thoughts before a conversation takes place even though they might share a common ground.

Using our multi-agent system, however, we can define a collaborative information space, the scope of actions, and the operational context within the agent’s technical environment since data and information sharing are a well solved problem. Technically

it easy for both communication partners to provide background information to each other's agents simultaneously.

Figure 11 introduces the concept of *Shared Thoughts*, which we incorporate into our agent-based communication model. The idea assumes that both participants in a conversation contribute their own personal insights and experiences – gathered independently and at different times – with the mutual goal of supporting collaborative interaction. By using these individual notes as *Shared Thoughts* within the conversational process, each participant enhances their communication capabilities through the assistance of their respective agents. This concept can be further developed by integrating past messages, documents, and other relevant materials into what we term a *Shared Conversation Knowledge Context*. This creates a supplementary content layer that builds upon the foundation of common ground. Importantly, our model is not confined to one-on-one exchanges; it is particularly relevant for organisations where collaboration and knowledge-intensive tasks are key. Conventional document management systems often fall short in actively supporting knowledge work. In contrast, our communication model offers a dynamic framework that can significantly contribute to future research in the areas of IC and management.

Figure 11 Organisational Knowledge as a Special Form of Shared Thoughts between two Communication Partners Emerges from Using Agent Augmented Communication

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Because existing communication models do not represent recently adopted technical devices for augmented communication, and because a notion of context knowledge is missing in these models, we describe an extended communication model, specifically to support future research in IC and corporate management research. Using the concepts and vocabulary of our communication model, it will be possible to conduct systematic research and to analyse the impact of particular LLMs and knowledge management techniques in the enterprise world within the context of a growing adoption of communication agents.

Figure 12 The Agent Augmented Communicator Inside an Organisational Context Embedded in a World of Public Knowledge

Using the three layers of digitally represented knowledge, we can define the communication scope and the boundaries of the multi-lateral communication system as well as the inner subsystem's boundaries as shown in Figure 12. With this, we can formalise our communication model. It consists of three directed information flows between the agents and the communication partner, where the agents are embedded

in and connected to a protected organisational context and a wider global context of public knowledge.

As shown in Figure 13 (a), we use three agent types, which link the communication partner to publicly available knowledge and to *Shared Thoughts*, which build a *Shared Communication Context*. Common communication hierarchies, as shown in Figure 13 (b), can be modelled in multiple ways, using our approach. Assuming, we possess appropriate metrics for describing the impact of changes in the way of how communication is managed, we can use our approach for quantitative studies. Figure 13 (c) illustrates an IC setup without hierarchy. It provides a multilateral and multidirectional communication context. Alternatively, Figure 13 (d) shows a clustered communication pattern in IC. The hierarchy seems to be preserved but the communication paths have opened and conversations are no longer bound to the hierarchical structure.

Experimental setups and quantitative analysis must be developed next in order to support future research.

We suggest to introduce new measures for evaluating the quality of an EIC, also including the new parameters, we make accessible with our model. For future management practice, the selection of the right LLM, an appropriate knowledge conservation and knowledge transfer methodology will be crucial success factors. Operational cost and complexity of maintenance of the AI infrastructure will both depend on the mentioned factors, hence it is important to understand their impact on IC.

(a) The atom of a universal communication structure

(b) Common communication hierarchies

(c) Augmented Group Communication Structure

(d) Augmented Hierarchical Communication Structure

Figure 13 Application of the new Multi-Agent Communication Model in IC and Management Research for Studies on Complex Communication Scenarios

With our communication model, we wish to emphasise the following advantages of an agents-augmented communication setup from a theoretical point of view since we believe that they might be confirmed through future empirical research:

- Increased efficiency in day-to-day operations due to decoupling and a reduction in time synchronisation.
- This leads to an optimised usage of resources and less waiting times.
- Knowledge conservation becomes an inherent part on the organisational level.
- On an individual level we can overcome cultural barriers and social distances.

- The cognitive capacity of the communication partners can virtually be extended or, in other words, the cognitive load during a conversation can be reduced by the agents.

Using our new communication model, we seek to initiate and foster an interdisciplinary dialogue at the intersection of communication, management, and technology research. Through the development of experiments and simulations grounded in our model, we expect that deeper insights will be gained in the dynamics of IC. Strengthening IC in this way has the potential to positively impact all facets of corporate communication, ultimately contributing to the establishment of an EIC framework. It is therefore essential to explore how agent-augmented communication influences managerial practices, organisational objectives, and overall performance.

Drawing inspiration from the success of ChatGPT and other LLM-based tools, we have structured our model around three core types of agents. This multi-agent approach enables us to capture and represent a wide range of communication scenarios within the context of IC. Notably, recent advancements in agent-based applications already demonstrate the use of multiple agents working collaboratively to complete complex tasks.

To avoid any confusion with other multi-agent system models, we briefly compare our approach with the Triad model, which focuses on collaborative problem-solving (Zong et al., 2024). In contrast, our agents operate within the communication framework of the individual communication partner to whom they are assigned. Their primary function is not to solve problems collectively, as in Triad, but rather to support and manage information flow to and from the communication partner within a communication-specific context.

Given the increasing number of multi-agent systems developed in recent years, it is essential to clearly differentiate our model. Each type of agent in our framework has a distinct role, managing specific aspects of the information flow, as illustrated in Figure 12. We deliberately refrain from discussing implementation details in this paper. Internally, an agent may consist of sub-agents, or alternatively, a comprehensive communication agent may be assigned to each person or organisational role. Our focus here is on the formal structuring of information flow and the localisation of knowledge – both of which contribute to the system’s memory and form the foundation of our communication model.

Given the inherent complexity of communication, we have adopted a multi-agent approach based on LLMs to address distinct components of the communication process. This structure enables systematic investigation into the roles and effects of individual agents, as well as the impact of their specific configurations. Each agent may operate with its own LLM, tailored to suit particular functional requirements. In our model, one type of agent is responsible for retrieving external information, another enhances or supplements the cognitive capacities of the communication partner, and a third type serves to represent and communicate that partner’s expertise externally. Owing to the multilingual capabilities of LLMs, such agent-based communication systems have the potential to bridge cultural gaps and promote faster cultural alignment – particularly in organisational and industrial contexts.

At the individual level, communication partners who make use of such an agent-based system benefit from a degree of decoupling from others – an especially valuable feature in emotionally charged situations. Increasingly, people struggle with affect regulation, and the support of a digital agent can assist in managing emotional responses more effectively. In high-stress or critical moments, this form of assistance

can serve as a protective mechanism, particularly when individuals may not be able to handle the situation unaided. Decoupling not only supports emotional regulation but also contributes to more efficient use of personal and organisational resources.

In addition to supporting emotional regulation, agents can also have a stimulating or motivating influence on users. One notable advantage of multi-agent communication systems lies in their ability to capture knowledge through stored communication data and automated reflection processes, particularly within asynchronous conversations.

Figure 14 Internal Corporate Communication (Welch & Jackson, 2007)

The Internal Corporate Communication (ICC) framework developed by Welch and Jackson (2007) (Figure 14) offers a structured approach to understanding IC within organisations. It emphasises the importance of communication roles, target stakeholder groups (such as employees, teams, line managers, and project groups), and the desired outcomes – such as employee engagement, commitment, and organisational effectiveness.

In contrast, our multi-agent communication model introduces a technologically enhanced perspective that integrates LLM-based agents into IC processes. While the ICC model is largely human-centric and grounded in traditional communication structures, our model extends these foundations by incorporating intelligent agents designed to support, mediate, and optimise communication dynamics.

Rather than positioning the two models in opposition, they may be seen as complementary. The ICC model provides a solid theoretical foundation and helps define the objectives and audiences for IC. Our multi-agent model, on the other hand, introduces the next stage in operationalising these objectives through intelligent augmentation. Agents can support the roles defined by ICC – such as line manager communication – by facilitating message delivery, improving comprehension, and capturing feedback automatically.

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